

Hydrogen Adsorption on the System $\text{Cu}-\text{V}_2\text{O}_3^{**}$

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Hydrogen adsorption has been studied in a volumetric adsorption unit at $98^\circ-250^\circ$ on the system $\text{Cu}-\text{V}_2\text{O}_3$, prepared *in situ* by the reduction of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 130° . Isotherms are of the Temkin type and isobars, constructed therefrom, show an activated adsorption, 175° being the temperature at which maximum coverage is possible (about 67% under an equilibrium pressure of 8.0 cm Hg.).

The kinetic data obtained by constant volume method at $102^\circ-290^\circ$ under different ambient pressures obey the Elovich equation showing break around $\theta = 0.09$, the break appearing at higher temperatures and higher initial pressures.

The nature of hydrogen adsorption has been correlated with the phase transition of V_2O_3 , occurring at $175^\circ-225^\circ$.

MORETTE and Strupler¹ have reported that copper orthovanadate can be reduced by hydrogen at $130^\circ-160^\circ$ to a mixture of copper and vanadium trioxide via the solid state reaction between Cu and V^{5+} . The catalytic activity of copper in hydrogenation-dehydrogenation reactions is well-known. Komarewsky et al.²⁻⁴ have demonstrated the catalytic activity of V_2O_3 in the dehydrosulphurisation of thiophene to butadiene, and in hydrogenation reactions. In this paper the authors have presented the results of hydrogen adsorption on this system of copper and vanadium trioxide obtained by the reduction of copper orthovanadate.

Experimental

1. *Preparation of the Sample*: Copper orthovanadate trihydrate of -100 to $+120$ mesh size B.S., prepared by the method described earlier⁵ was evacuated in a volumetric adsorption apparatus at 400° and a pressure of 10^{-5} torr for 60 hours. Then the temperature was lowered to 130° and the system was treated with pure and dry hydrogen under a constant pressure of 40 cm. After equilibrium was established, the system was evacuated at 400° and 10^{-5} torr for several hrs. After the evacuation the system was again cooled to 130° and treated with hydrogen in the same way as before. The process was repeated several times until the equilibrium volume of hydrogen was quantitatively reproducible. (The total volume of hydrogen uptake agreed, within experimental error, with the stoichiometric requirements of the reduction of

$\text{Cu}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2$ to a mixture of Cu and V_2O_3 . The presence of Cu and V_2O_3 phases and the absence of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2$ phase after reduction were confirmed by X-ray analysis).

2. *Adsorption apparatus and measurement of adsorption*: The apparatus used was a volumetric BET unit, equipped with McLeod gauge and mercury diffusion pump, backed by Edwards rotary high vacuum pump. Liquid nitrogen traps were provided between the system and the diffusion pump.

Gases like nitrogen, helium, and hydrogen used for the dead space, surface area and adsorption measurements were purified from commercial varieties by the usual procedure.

Adsorption studies have been made on 3 gm of $\text{Cu}_3(\text{VO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reduced *in situ* by hydrogen as described above. Before each measurement, as a standard procedure, the system was evacuated at 350° and 10^{-5} torr for 6 hrs.

Results

The surface area of the reduced copper vanadate, determined by the low-temperature nitrogen adsorption technique, was found to be $10.88 \text{ m}^2/\text{gm}$. If the ratio of the cross-section⁶ of adsorbed hydrogen to that of adsorbed nitrogen is taken as 0.54, the volume of hydrogen for monolayer formation is 4.55 ml/gm .

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Below 100° the adsorption is too slow for any kinetic measurement and the establishment of equilibrium conditions takes quite a long time. However, adsorption isotherms have been measured at 98° , 150° , 175° , 200° and 250° upto an equilibrium pressure of 8 cm Hg. The volume adsorbed varies approximately in a linear way with $\log P_{\text{mm}}$. The isotherms are of Temkin type and are shown in Fig. 1A from which it is seen that at a given equilibrium pressure, volume of hydrogen adsorbed increases from 98° to 175° , then decreases gradually upto 250° . This is also evident from the adsorption isobars in Fig. 1B. At 175° about 67% coverage is possible at an equilibrium pressure of 8 cm Hg.

Fig. 1A. Hydrogen adsorption isotherms on reduced copper vanadate.

Fig. 1B. Hydrogen adsorption isobars on reduced copper vanadate.

The kinetics of hydrogen adsorption have been measured under constant volume conditions at different temperatures and different initial pressures. The kinetic

data agree well with the modified Elovich equation of Cimino *et al*⁷;

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = a^* \exp [-\alpha(q - q_0)] \quad (1)$$

which upon integration gives

$$q - q_0 = 1/\alpha \ln (1 + t/t_0) \quad (2)$$

where q = volume of gas adsorbed at time t ,

q_0 = volume of gas adsorbed instantaneously at $t=0$,

α = constant denoting the deceleration of the adsorption process,

t_0 = arbitrary constant required for linearising q vs $\log t$ plots

and a^* = initial rate of uptake = $1/\alpha t_0$.

The kinetic data do not fit in any other rate equation which is applicable under constant volume condition. The Elovich plots of q vs $\log (t+t_0)$ are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 and the Elovich parameters are shown in Table-1.

(a) *Effect of temperature*: The Elovich plots show breaks at 150° , 178° and 214° for $P_0 = 6.70$ cm and for all initial pressures at 178° and 214° except 3.79 cm at 214° (Figs. 2 and 3). From 250° and above the

Fig. 2. Elovich plots hydrogen chemisorption on reduced copper vanadate at different temperatures

first kinetic stage disappears and rather a third stage appears at higher coverage. The rate of the second kinetic process is greater than the first one ($\alpha_I > \alpha_{II}$). But α_{II} values increase gradually with temperature from 178° to 290° so that the rate constant of the second kinetic process has a negative temperature coefficient while α_I decreases gradually with temperature from 102° to 214°.

Fig. 3. Effect of initial pressure on the kinetics of chemisorption of hydrogen on reduced copper vanadate at 178°C and 214°C.

(b) *Analysis of the Elovich break*: Firstly, the occurrence of break is a phenomenon from 150° onwards and it is not due to the deviation of Elovich data near equilibrium condition (Table-1). At 150° the break appears at $\theta=0.073$; at 178°, at $\theta=0.104$; and at 214°, at $\theta=0.081$. Secondly, the ratio of the no. of mole adsorbed by the first process to the total no. of molecules adsorbed upto 120 min, at which time equilibrium is nearly attained, (q_b/q_{120}), decreases rapidly with temperature. That is, the activity of the second type of sites increases rapidly with temperature whereas that of the first type of sites remains nearly constant except that it is slightly higher at 178°.

(c) *Effect of initial pressure*: From Table 1 the Elovich constant decreases with increasing initial

pressure for both the processes. On the assumption $\alpha = k P_0^{-n}$, where $-n_{\alpha} = \text{constant}$, the plots of $\log \alpha$ vs $\log P_0$ are shown for both the stages at 178° and 214° in Fig. 4. At both temperatures the variation of α with P_0 is the same for a particular kinetic stage and is nearly same for both the processes, though at the second stage, α_{II} is a little more dependent on P_0 . However, the values of $-n_{\alpha}$ (Fig. 4) suggest a molecular adsorption rather than a dissociative one.

Fig. 4. Variation of Elovich constant (α) with initial pressure (P_0) of hydrogen in the kinetics of chemisorption of hydrogen on reduced copper vanadate

From Table 1, t_0 values are observed to decrease regularly with increasing temperature and to be nearly independent of initial pressure at a constant temperature. Such variation may signify t_0 being the reciprocal of the mean life-time of the adsorbed species⁷ rather than the time-lag at which Elovich equation holds for the kinetic data.

Discussion

As has been mentioned earlier, the reduction of copper orthovanadate, at 130° by hydrogen leads to the formation of a mixture of metallic copper and V_2O_5 . Though copper films do not take up hydrogen at room temperature, the reduction in sorption of hydrogen by copper powders obtained from copper salts have been reported⁸ repeatedly even at 0°. Moreover, in case of lowering of the work-function of a given metal by oxygen adsorption, oxygen acts as the promoter for the adsorption of a gas which forms a double layer negative outwards⁹. For hydrogen chemisorption on copper the latter requirement is fulfilled, and Fianda and Lange¹⁰ have shown that oxygen adsorption lowers the work-function of copper. So in this case where adsorbed oxygen in small quantity may easily remain on the

TABLE I—ELOVICH PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND INITIAL PRESSURES

Temp. °C	P_0 (cm of Hg)	t_0 (min)	$\alpha_1 \times 10^{-6}$ (moles ⁻¹ gm)	$\alpha_1 \times 10^{-6}$ (moles ⁻¹ gm)	$\alpha_1/\alpha_1 t$	t_b (min)	$q_b \times 10^5$ (moles gm ⁻¹)	$q_b/N_m(\text{H}_2)$ $\times 100$ (moles gm ⁻¹)	$q_{120} \times 10^5$ (moles gm ⁻¹)	q_b/q_{120} $\times 100$	$q_t \times 10^6$ (moles gm ⁻¹)	$q_c \times 10^6$ (moles gm ⁻¹)	$\alpha_1^2 \times 10^7$ (moles gm ⁻¹ min ⁻¹)
102	6.70	12.0	0.920	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.660	5.558	0.909
122	6.70	16.0	0.435	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.644	5.513	1.437
150	6.70	14.0	0.201	0.126	1.595	75.1	1.49	7.35	1.964	95.52	6.452	6.09	3.555
178	4.48	5.5	0.181	0.137	1.321	49.4	1.60	7.87	2.160	73.99	3.954	3.024	10.07
178	5.50	6.0	0.151	0.109	1.235	35.7	1.72	8.65	2.720	63.19	5.978	4.958	11.04
178	6.70	6.0	0.127	0.088	1.443	41.9	2.12	10.43	3.251	65.16	6.220	4.99	13.10
178	9.11	6.5	0.099	0.059	1.678	51.0	2.64	12.99	3.50	75.48	9.234	7.794	13.52
214	3.79	3.0	0.158	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	5.614	3.789	21.14
214	5.01	3.0	0.132	0.139	0.949	18.9	1.92	9.45	3.45	55.94	6.935	5.142	25.25
214	6.70	3.0	0.102	0.096	1.063	7.50	1.65	8.12	3.62	45.59	7.558	4.738	28.95
214	8.72	3.0	0.079	0.065	1.201	14.38	2.25	11.08	3.85	58.46	12.803	9.153	42.42
250	6.70	1.6	—	0.132	—	—	—	—	—	—	11.021	5.77	47.3
290	6.70	0.1	—	0.152	—	—	—	—	—	—	19.550	3.54	65.66

copper surface during its reduction with hydrogen at 130°, it is likely that adsorption of hydrogen on copper is highly facilitated and may commence before the adsorption of hydrogen on V₂O₅ sets in. But the changeover from the Cu-site to V₂O₅-site should involve a drastic change in the nature of adsorption which is missing upto 70% coverage as shown in Fig. 1. Moreover, the activation energy is observed to be about 13 Kcal/mole on the average, whereas Lennard-Jones¹¹ has estimated it to be about 5 Kcal/mole for H₂/Cu adsorption. So, the initial fast adsorption, q₀, which is nearly independent of temperature upto 250° may be due to this adsorption of hydrogen on copper with the formation of resonating covalent bonds between the adsorbed hydrogen atom and the metallic copper lattice and the rest of the adsorption process may take place on V₂O₅ alone.

V₂O₅ is an n-type semiconductor with excess electrons due to anion vacancies. The electrical conductivity of V₂O₅ suggests metallic conduction to some extent. Arnold and Mires¹² have observed a transition of V₂O₅ along and perpendicular to the trigonal axis at 175°-225° and according to Hyland¹³, at the temperature of phase transition (T_t) the thermal ionisation of electrons (out of the localised states into delocalised band states) becomes a co-operative process and the population of the d-band increases catastrophically leading to a reversible 1st order phase transition into the metallic state.

Apparently the decrease in the volume of gas adsorbed at a given equilibrium pressure above 175° (Fig. 1) or the break in the Elovich plots in the temperature range 150°-290° (Fig. 2) is due to this phase transition of V₂O₅ at 175°-225°. In the temperature range 150°-214° adsorption of hydrogen induces the phase transition, by increasing the electron concentration of the solid matrix until it causes a "cascade", the amount of hydrogen needed for such induction being lower at higher temperature. At sufficiently high temperatures this effect of adsorbed hydrogen diminishes due to inherent transition at these temperatures, so that the ratio α_I/α_{II} decreases gradually with temperature (Table 1).

The second kinetic stage probably concerns with the involvement of the metallic electrons and, due to negative temperature co-efficient of the electron mobility, the deceleration constant, α_{II} , increases with temperature. This involvement may consist of the formation of a

purely covalent bond between the hydrogen atom and the lattice or the formation of resonating covalent bonds of Pauling-type with the complete collectivisation and delocalisation of all electrons throughout the lattice. But these are unlikely in view of the facts that hydrogen is strongly adsorbed to about 70% coverage and that the adsorbed layer is nearly immobile. The high coverage suggests a cumulative chemisorption¹⁴, a case of electron transfer from the adsorbed hydrogen to the lattice, thus explaining the decrease in the volume of hydrogen adsorbed after the electron concentration of the solid matrix has increased enormously due to phase transition at 175°-225°.

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